

APACHE

SOLR

BY AUGMENT SYSTEMS

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Solr Terminology

There are several terms associated with Solr implementation which you will come across, let's understand them better.

- **Core:** It is a running instance of a Lucene index along with all the Solr configuration (SolrConfigXml, SchemaXml, etc...). In simple terms, Core is basically an index of the text and fields found in documents. A single Solr application can contain 0 or more cores which are run largely in isolation but can communicate with each other if necessary via the Core Container.
- **Collection:** Collection is a complete logical index in a SolrCloud cluster. It is associated with a config set and is made up of one or more shards.
- **Shards:** A shard is logical division of the collection, containing a subset of documents from the collection, such that every document in a collection is contained in exactly one Shard. Each shard is made up of one or more replicas.
- **Nodes:** A node is Java Virtual Machine instance running solr in cloud mode. It is also called a server. Each Solr core can also be considered a node.
- **Replicas:** Replica is one copy of a shard. Each replica exists within Solr as a core.
- **Cluster:** A set of Solr nodes is called a Cluster. It is managed by ZooKeeper as a single unit. When you have a cluster, you can always make requests to the cluster and if the request is acknowledged, you can be sure that it will be managed as a unit and be durable, i.e., you won't lose data.
- **Index:** A Solr index is the object used for indexing and retrieving information. It contains data from many different sources, including XML files, comma-separated value (CSV) files, data extracted a database, and files formats such as Microsoft Word or PDF.

- **Field:** Solr's basic unit of information that is a document composed of "fields". When you add a document, Solr takes the information in the document's fields and adds that information to an index.
- **Schema:** Schema tells the Solr how it should build indexes from input documents.
- **Port:** The default port for running solr is 8983.
- **Client-Server:** In network Architecture, Client/server is a program relationship in which one program that is the Client requests a service from another program that is Server.
- **Zookeeper:** It is a distributed coordinated service for maintaining configuration information, providing distributed synchronization, and providing group services to large number of hosts.

Apache Solr

1. Getting started with Solr6: Download & Installation

Apache Solr is a replication and load-balancing querying software which builds on another open source technology Lucene managed by Apache Software Foundation (www.apache.org). Apache Solr is a fast, fault tolerant, scalable and highly reliable software product which provides automated failover and recovery centralized configuration and comes with an inbuilt Jetty server.

The Lucene search engine is an open source Java based full-text search library which provides an easy add document search capability to an application or website.

Apache Solr comes with a wide set of high impact features such as

- Advanced Full-Text Search capabilities.
- Optimized for High Volume traffic
- Standard based open interfaces - XML, JSON & HTTP.
- Comprehensive Administration Interfaces
- Easy Monitoring.
- Highly Scalable and Fault Tolerant.
- Flexible and Adaptable with easy configuration.
- Near Real - Time Indexing.
- Extensible Plug-in Architecture.

listed on <http://lucene.apache.org/solr/>.

Apache Solr has now become a software used worldwide by most of the major companies to index and search data using their website or application.

Following companies are using Apache Solr in their website and applications for various purpose as listed below:

NASA is using Solr as the Enterprise Search component in its NEBULA cloud computing platform.

AOL is using Solr to power its channels.

Cisco uses Solr at the core for social network search platform.

Chegg uses Solr for their site search feature for services.

Netflix uses Solr for their site search feature.

Reddit uses Solr for search.

Apple is using Solr.

FCC.gov website featuring Solr powered search and faceted navigation.

jobseeker.com.au has its search engine powered by Solr 3.5.

Instagram a Facebook company, uses Solr to power it's geo-search API.

Panasonic Europe uses Solr to power the search and faceted navigation on it's sites for 30 countries.

Whitehouse uses Solr via Drupal for site search w/highlighting & faceting.

Salesforce is using Solr.

EMC is using Solr.

Cnet use Solr for product search and faceted browsing.

As listed by Lucidworks on January 21, 2012.

This tutorial is designed for Linux users worldwide, covering the following topics.

- Downloading Solr 6.3.0
- Installing Solr 6.3.0
- A Quick Overview of Solr 6.3.0
- Integrating Solr with an application

1. Downloading Solr 6.3.0

Prerequisites:

- **Java 7 or greater**
You can download JDK (Java Development Kit) from the Oracle's official website on the download page under "Java SE Downloads".
- **CentOS, Cygwin (Optional)**
Most of the examples in Solr official documentation make use of the UNIX environment. UNIX-like environment is not a prerequisite for Solr but it is helpful with the ability to follow certain documentation examples, testing, and getting help from the user forum.
- **Curl (Optional)**
Curl is a Unix command line utility for sending HTTP requests, testing examples when performance is not important.

Download the latest Solr release from the Apache download mirror <http://ftp.jaist.ac.jp/pub/apache/lucene/solr/6.3.0/>

Index of /pub/apache/lucene/solr/6.3.0

Name	Last modified	Size	Description
Parent Directory	-	-	-
changes/	2016-11-08 14:15	-	-
solr-6.3.0-src.tgz	2016-11-03 01:33	40M	-
solr-6.3.0.tgz	2016-11-03 01:33	139M	-
solr-6.3.0.zip	2016-11-03 01:33	148M	-

Apache/2.4.25 (Unix) OpenSSL/1.0.2j-fips Server at ftp.jaist.ac.jp Port 80

2. Installing Solr 6.3.0

This section describes the procedure to install Solr 6.3.0 in your system.

Unpack Solr 6.3.0.zip

3.A Quick Overview of Solr 6.3.0

Once finished with download and installation of Solr 6.3.0, you can walk through Solr 6.3.0 directory.

- **bin folder**

The `bin` folder in Solr directory contains the scripts to Start and Stop the Solr Server at your system.

- **server & logs folder**

The `server` folder in Solr directory contains the `logs` folder where all the logs are written after starting Solr. The logs can be helpful to check for any error during implementation of Solr.

- **example folder**

The `example` folder consists of few example files which can be used to illustrate how Solr indexes the data present in the documents.

- **solr & server folder**

The `solr` folder under server directory contains different collections or cores created to be deployed by the application. The configuration and data for each of the core/ collection are stored in the respective core/ collection folder.

- **exampledocs folder**

The `exampledocs` folder under `example` directory provides set of files to be posted to Solr core or collection.

4. Integrating Solr with an Application

- **Schema.** The schema tells Solr about the contents of documents it will be indexing. Solr contains default schema such as basic configs, data driven schema configs, sample tech products configs.
- **Deploying Solr** to your website or application.
- **Posting documents** for which your users will search on Solr.
- **Configuring search capability** in your website or application.

2. Starting Solr in Standalone Mode

This section describes how to run Solr in Standalone Mode. This can be achieved by running Solr independently without zookeeper where you have a single core for each index.

In this section, we will discuss about the standalone server and core, to run Solr with an example schema, how to add documents, and how to run queries. When the Solr server is started in Standalone mode the created configuration is called core and when it is started in SolrCloud mode the created configuration is called Collection.

1.Starting Solr Server

Solr server can be started by running following command in the bin directory from the Solr directory.

```
$ bin/solr start
```


The image shows a terminal window titled "rakesh@localhost:~/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/bin". The terminal output is as follows:

```
[rakesh@localhost ~]$ cd Desktop/solr-6.3.0/bin
[rakesh@localhost bin]$ ./solr start
Archiving 1 old GC log files to /home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/server/logs/archived
Archiving 1 console log files to /home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/server/logs/archived
Rotating solr logs, keeping a max of 9 generations
Waiting up to 180 seconds to see Solr running on port 8983 [/]
Started Solr server on port 8983 (pid=5729). Happy searching!

[rakesh@localhost bin]$
```

This will start Solr, listening on default port 8983.

Now, let's open the Solr GUI by logging into localhost:8983 in the web browser.

2. Using Solr Help

Use help command for specific usage instructions of Solr

`$ bin/solr start -help`

```
[rakesh@localhost bin]$ ./solr start -help
Usage: solr start [-f] [-c] [-h hostname] [-p port] [-d directory] [-z zkHost] [-m memory] [-e example] [-s solr.solr.home] [-a "additional-options"] [-V]

-f          Start Solr in foreground; default starts Solr in the background
           and sends stdout / stderr to solr-PORT-console.log

-c or -cloud Start Solr in SolrCloud mode; if -z not supplied, an embedded Zookeeper
           instance is started on Solr port+1000, such as 9983 if Solr is bound to 8983

-h <host>   Specify the hostname for this Solr instance

-p <port>   Specify the port to start the Solr HTTP listener on; default is 8983
           The specified port (SOLR_PORT) will also be used to determine the stop port
           STOP_PORT=(SOLR_PORT-1000) and JMX RMI listen port RMI_PORT=(SOLR_PORT+10000).
           For instance, if you set -p 8985, then the STOP_PORT=7985 and RMI_PORT=18985

-d <dir>    Specify the Solr server directory; defaults to server

-z <zkHost> Zookeeper connection string; only used when running in SolrCloud mode using -c
           To launch an embedded Zookeeper instance, don't pass this parameter.

-m <memory> Sets the min (-Xms) and max (-Xmx) heap size for the JVM, such as: -m 4g
           results in: -Xms4g -Xmx4g; by default, this script sets the heap size to 512m

-s <dir>    Sets the solr.solr.home system property; Solr will create core directories under
```

```
Applications ▾ Places ▾ Terminal ▾ Mon 10:18 AM
rakesh@localhost:~/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/bin
File Edit View Search Terminal Help

-m <memory> Sets the min (-Xms) and max (-Xmx) heap size for the JVM, such as: -m 4g
             results in: -Xms4g -Xmx4g; by default, this script sets the heap size to 512m

-s <dir>     Sets the solr.solr.home system property; Solr will create core directories under
             this directory. This allows you to run multiple Solr instances on the same host
             while reusing the same server directory set using the -d parameter. If set, the
             specified directory should contain a solr.xml file, unless solr.xml exists in Zookeeper.
             This parameter is ignored when running examples (-e), as the solr.solr.home depends
             on which example is run. The default value is server/solr.

-e <example> Name of the example to run; available examples:
             cloud: SolrCloud example
             techproducts: Comprehensive example illustrating many of Solr's core capabilities
             dih: Data Import Handler
             schemaless: Schema-less example

-a          Additional parameters to pass to the JVM when starting Solr, such as to setup
             Java debug options. For example, to enable a Java debugger to attach to the Solr JVM
             you could pass: -a "-agentlib:jwp=transport=dt_socket,server=y,suspend=n,address=18983"
             In most cases, you should wrap the additional parameters in double quotes.

-noprompt   Don't prompt for input; accept all defaults when running examples that accept user input

-v and -q   Verbose (-v) or quiet (-q) logging. Sets default log level to DEBUG or WARN instead of INFO

-V or -verbose Verbose messages from this script

[rakesh@localhost bin]$
```

3.Starting Solr Server with a Different Port

We can change the port Solr listens on, by giving -p as a parameter to Solr start command.

```
$ bin/solr start -p 8984
```

```
Applications ▾ Places ▾ Terminal ▾ Mon 10:17 AM
rakesh@localhost:~/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/bin
File Edit View Search Terminal Help

[rakesh@localhost bin]$ ./solr start -p 8984
Archiving 1 old GC log files to /home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/server/logs/archived
Archiving 1 console log files to /home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/server/logs/archived
Rotating solr logs, keeping a max of 9 generations
Waiting up to 180 seconds to see Solr running on port 8984 [-]
Started Solr server on port 8984 (pid=6005). Happy searching!

[rakesh@localhost bin]$
```

4. Stopping Solr Instance

To stop Solr instance running on a specific port use `-p` parameter with Solr stop command.

```
$ bin/solr stop -p 8983
```



```
Applications Places Terminal Mon 10:20 AM
rakesh@localhost:~/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/bin
File Edit View Search Terminal Help
[rakesh@localhost bin]$ ./solr stop -p 8983
Sending stop command to Solr running on port 8983 ... waiting up to 180 seconds to allow Jetty process 5729 to stop gracefully.
[rakesh@localhost bin]$
```

5. Creating Core in Solr

We will use the `-c` parameter to create a core in Solr.

```
$ bin/solr create_core -c core1
```



```
Applications Places Terminal Sat 12:07 PM
rakesh@localhost:~/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/bin
File Edit View Search Terminal Help
[rakesh@localhost ~]$ cd Desktop/solr-6.3.0/bin
[rakesh@localhost bin]$ ./solr start -p 8983
Waiting up to 180 seconds to see Solr running on port 8983 [-]
Started Solr server on port 8983 (pid=7780). Happy searching!

[rakesh@localhost bin]$ ./solr create_core -c Core1

Copying configuration to new core instance directory:
/home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/server/solr/Core1

Creating new core 'Core1' using command:
http://localhost:8983/solr/admin/cores?action=CREATE&name=Core1&instanceDir=Core1

{
  "responseHeader":{
    "status":0,
    "QTime":5335,
    "core":"Core1"}

[rakesh@localhost bin]$
```

Now, let's check the Solr GUI for created core named as Core1.

The screenshot shows the Solr Admin interface in a Mozilla Firefox browser. The address bar displays `localhost:8983/solr/#/cores/Core1`. The main content area shows the configuration for 'Core1'. At the top, there are buttons for 'Add Core', 'Unload', 'Rename', 'Swap', and 'Reload'. Below these, the 'Core' section lists the following details:

- startTime: less than a minute ago
- instanceDir: /home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/server/solr/Core1
- dataDir: /home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/server/solr/Core1/data

The 'Index' section shows the following details:

- lastModified: -
- version: 2
- numDocs: 0
- maxDoc: 0
- deletedDocs: 0
- optimized: ✓
- current: ✓
- directory: org.apache.lucene.store.NRTCachingDirectory:NRTCachingDirectory(MMapDirectory@/home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/server/solr/Core1/data/index lockFactory=org.apache.lucene.store.NativeFSLockFactory@510844a9; maxCacheMB=48.0

6. Posting Documents in the Core

`$ bin/post -c core1 example/exampledocs/*.xml`

The screenshot shows a terminal window with the following output:

```
[rakesh@localhost bin]$ cd ..
[rakesh@localhost solr-6.3.0]$ ./bin/post -c core1 example/exampledocs/*.xml
/usr/java/jdk1.8.0_66/bin/java -classpath /home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/dist/solr-core-6.3.0.jar -Dauto=yes -Dc=core1 -Ddata=files org.apache.solr.r
t.tl.SimplePostTool example/exampledocs/gb18030-example.xml example/exampledocs/hd.xml example/exampledocs/ipod_other.xml example/exampledocs/ipod_vid
e
o.xml example/exampledocs/manufacturers.xml example/exampledocs/mem.xml example/exampledocs/money.xml example/exampledocs/monitor2.xml example/example
docs/monitor.xml example/exampledocs/mp500.xml example/exampledocs/sd500.xml example/exampledocs/solr.xml example/exampledocs/utf8-example.xml example
/exampledocs/vidcard.xml
SimplePostTool version 5.0.0
Posting files to [base] url http://localhost:8983/solr/core1/update...
Entering auto mode. File endings considered are xml,json,jsonl,csv,pdf,doc,docx,ppt,pptx,xls,xlsx,odt,odp,ods,ott,otp,ots,rtf,htm,html,txt,log
POSTing file gb18030-example.xml (application/xml) to [base]
POSTing file hd.xml (application/xml) to [base]
POSTing file ipod_other.xml (application/xml) to [base]
POSTing file ipod_video.xml (application/xml) to [base]
POSTing file manufacturers.xml (application/xml) to [base]
POSTing file mem.xml (application/xml) to [base]
POSTing file money.xml (application/xml) to [base]
POSTing file monitor2.xml (application/xml) to [base]
POSTing file monitor.xml (application/xml) to [base]
POSTing file mp500.xml (application/xml) to [base]
POSTing file sd500.xml (application/xml) to [base]
POSTing file solr.xml (application/xml) to [base]
POSTing file utf8-example.xml (application/xml) to [base]
POSTing file vidcard.xml (application/xml) to [base]
14 files indexed.
COMMITting Solr index changes to http://localhost:8983/solr/core1/update...
Time spent: 0:00:04.938
[rakesh@localhost solr-6.3.0]$
```

Now, let's explore Solr GUI to check number of documents posted to core1.

The screenshot shows the Solr Admin interface in a Mozilla Firefox browser. The address bar displays `localhost:8983/solr/#/core1`. The page features a sidebar with navigation options: Dashboard, Logging, Core Admin, Java Properties, Thread Dump, and a Core Selector set to `core1`. The main content area is divided into several sections:

- Statistics:** Last Modified: 2 minutes ago, Num Docs: 32, Max Doc: 32, Heap Memory: -1, Usage: Deleted Docs: 0, Version: 6, Segment Count: 1. Status indicators show 'Optimized: ✓' and 'Current: ✓'.
- Instance:** CWD: `/home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/server`, Instance: `/home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/server/solr/core1`, Data: `/home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/server/solr/core1/data`, Index: `/home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/server/solr/core1/data/index`, Impl: `org.apache.solr.core.NRTCachingDirectoryFactory`.
- Replication (Master):** A table showing replication details:

	Version	Gen	Size
Master (Searching)	148339233740	2	35.66 KB
Master (Replicable)	148339233740	2	-
- Healthcheck:** Ping request handler is not configured with a healthcheck file.

The bottom of the browser window shows the taskbar with the current window titled 'Solr Admin - Mozilla Firefox' and other open applications like 'example' and 'Pictures'.

This screenshot shows the Solr Admin interface at the `localhost:8983/solr/#/~cores/core1` path. The sidebar highlights 'Core Admin' and includes a 'Core Selector' dropdown. The main content area displays configuration and status for the selected core:

- Core:** startTime: 4 minutes ago, instanceDir: `/home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/server/solr/core1`, dataDir: `/home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/server/solr/core1/data`. Action buttons for 'Add Core', 'Unload', 'Rename', 'Swap', and 'Reload' are visible at the top.
- Index:** lastModified: 2 minutes ago, version: 6, numDocs: 32, maxDoc: 32, deletedDocs: 0, optimized: ✓, current: ✓. The directory path is `org.apache.lucene.store.NRTCachingDirectory.NRTCachingDirectory(MMapDirectory@/home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/server/solr/core1/data/index lockFactory=org.apache.lucene.store.NativeFSLockFactory@6f6ea3f6; maxCacheMB=48.0`.

The browser taskbar at the bottom shows the window title 'Solr Admin - Mozilla Firefox' and the same set of open applications as the previous screenshot.

7. Running Query on the Documents

We can run the desired query in the -q field of the Solr GUI query panel.

Once the query is executed we get the following result.

8. Deleting Solr Core

We can delete the core previously created by using `-c` parameter with `delete` command in Solr.

`$ bin/solr delete -c core1 -p 8983`

9.Starting Solr with a Specific Bundled Example Configuration Set

Solr introduced a provision to create a set of sharable configuration files called Config Sets, that can be used to create new cores. The example configurations allow to get started with a configuration that mirrors what you want to accomplish with Solr.

We can launch the examples using `-e <example>` flag where `<example>` is the name of the example to run; available examples are:

- **Cloud: SolrCloud example**
The cloud example starts a 1-4 node SolrCloud cluster on a single system. An interactive session will be initiated to take you through options to select an initial config set to start with.
- **Techproducts: Comprehensive example illustrating many of Solr's core capabilities.**
The Techproducts example starts Solr in standalone mode. It starts Solr schema designed for the sample documents included in `exampledocs` directory under `example` directory from Solr. The configuration used can be found in `sample_techproducts_configs` directory.
- **Dih: Data Import Handler**
The Data Import Handler (DIH) provides a mechanism for extracting data from a data store and indexing it. DIH can index content from Relational Database, HTTP based data sources such as RSS and ATOM feeds, e-mail repositories, and structured XML.
- **Schemaless: Schema-less example**
The Schemaless example starts Solr in standalone mode using a managed schema, and provides a very minimal pre-defined schema.

Now, let's run Solr with these example configurations.

- To launch the "techproducts" example, we would do:
\$ bin/solr -e techproducts


```
rakesh@localhost:~/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/bin

[rakesh@localhost bin]$ ./solr start -e techproducts
Creating Solr home directory /home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/example/techproducts/solr

Starting up Solr on port 8983 using command:
/home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/bin/solr start -p 8983 -s "/home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/example/techproducts/solr"

Waiting up to 180 seconds to see Solr running on port 8983 [-]
Started Solr server on port 8983 (pid=6627). Happy searching!

Copying configuration to new core instance directory:
/home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/example/techproducts/solr/techproducts

Creating new core 'techproducts' using command:
http://localhost:8983/solr/admin/cores?action=CREATE&name=techproducts&instanceDir=techproducts

{
  "responseHeader":{
    "status":0,
    "QTime":9061},
  "core":"techproducts"}

Indexing tech product example docs from /home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/example/exampledocs
SimplePostTool version 5.0.0
Posting files to [base] url http://localhost:8983/solr/techproducts/update using content-type application/xml...
POSTing file gb18030-example.xml to [base]
POSTing file hd.xml to [base]
```



```
"responseHeader":{
  "status":0,
  "QTime":9061},
"core":"techproducts"}

Indexing tech product example docs from /home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/example/exampledocs
SimplePostTool version 5.0.0
Posting files to [base] url http://localhost:8983/solr/techproducts/update using content-type application/xml...
POSTing file gb18030-example.xml to [base]
POSTing file hd.xml to [base]
POSTing file ipod_other.xml to [base]
POSTing file ipod_video.xml to [base]
POSTing file manufacturers.xml to [base]
POSTing file mem.xml to [base]
POSTing file money.xml to [base]
POSTing file monitor.xml to [base]
POSTing file monitor2.xml to [base]
POSTing file mp500.xml to [base]
POSTing file sd500.xml to [base]
POSTing file solr.xml to [base]
POSTing file utf8-example.xml to [base]
POSTing file vidcard.xml to [base]
14 files indexed.
COMMITting Solr index changes to http://localhost:8983/solr/techproducts/update...
Time spent: 0:00:02.069

Solr techproducts example launched successfully. Direct your Web browser to http://localhost:8983/solr to visit the Solr Admin UI
[rakesh@localhost bin]$
```

- To launch the "dih" example, you would do:
\$ bin/solr -e dih


```
rakesh@localhost:~/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/bin
File Edit View Search Terminal Help
[rakesh@localhost bin]$ ./solr -e dih
Starting up Solr on port 8983 using command:
/home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/bin/solr start -p 8983 -s "/home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/example/example-DIH/solr"
Archiving 1 old GC log files to /home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/example/example-DIH/solr/../logs/archived
Archiving 1 console log files to /home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/example/example-DIH/solr/../logs/archived
Rotating solr logs, keeping a max of 9 generations
Waiting up to 180 seconds to see Solr running on port 8983 [/]
Started Solr server on port 8983 (pid=8994). Happy searching!

Solr dih example launched successfully. Direct your Web browser to http://localhost:8983/solr to visit the Solr Admin UI
[rakesh@localhost bin]$
[rakesh@localhost bin]$
```

- To launch the "schemaless" example, you would do:
\$ bin/solr -e schemaless


```
rakesh@localhost:~/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/bin
File Edit View Search Terminal Help
[rakesh@localhost bin]$ ./solr -e schemaless
Solr home directory /home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/example/schemaless/solr already exists.
Starting up Solr on port 8983 using command:
/home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/bin/solr start -p 8983 -s "/home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/example/schemaless/solr"
Waiting up to 180 seconds to see Solr running on port 8983 [/]
Started Solr server on port 8983 (pid=9478). Happy searching!

Copying configuration to new core instance directory:
/home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/example/schemaless/solr/gettingstarted
Creating new core 'gettingstarted' using command:
http://localhost:8983/solr/admin/cores?action=CREATE&name=gettingstarted&instanceDir=gettingstarted
{
  "responseHeader":{
    "status":0,
    "QTime":8805},
  "core":"gettingstarted"}

Solr schemaless example launched successfully. Direct your Web browser to http://localhost:8983/solr to visit the Solr Admin UI
[rakesh@localhost bin]$
```

- To launch the "cloud" example, you would do:
\$ bin/solr -e cloud


```
rakesh@localhost:~/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/bin
File Edit View Search Terminal Help
[rakesh@localhost bin]$ ./solr -e cloud

Welcome to the SolrCloud example!

This interactive session will help you launch a SolrCloud cluster on your local workstation.
To begin, how many Solr nodes would you like to run in your local cluster? (specify 1-4 nodes) [2]:
2
Ok, let's start up 2 Solr nodes for your example SolrCloud cluster.
Please enter the port for node1 [8983]:
8983
Please enter the port for node2 [7574]:
7574
Solr home directory /home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/example/cloud/node1/solr already exists.
/home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/example/cloud/node2 already exists.

Starting up Solr on port 8983 using command:
/home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/bin/solr start -cloud -p 8983 -s "/home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/example/cloud/node1/solr"

Archiving 1 old GC log files to /home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/example/cloud/node1/solr/../logs/archived
Archiving 1 console log files to /home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/example/cloud/node1/solr/../logs/archived
Rotating solr logs, keeping a max of 9 generations
Waiting up to 180 seconds to see Solr running on port 8983 [/]
Started Solr server on port 8983 (pid=13135). Happy searching!

Starting up Solr on port 7574 using command:
/home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/bin/solr start -cloud -p 7574 -s "/home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/example/cloud/node2/solr" -z localhost:9983

Archiving 1 old GC log files to /home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/example/cloud/node2/solr/../logs/archived
```

This topic we have explained in detail in Section 3.

10. Checking Solr Server Status

To check if Solr is running locally, we can use the status command:

\$ bin/solr status


```
rakesh@localhost:~/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/bin
File Edit View Search Terminal Help
[rakesh@localhost bin]$ ./solr status

Found 2 Solr nodes:

Solr process 13135 running on port 8983
{
  "solr_home": "/home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/example/cloud/node1/solr",
  "version": "6.3.0 a66a44513ee8191e25b477372094bfa846450316 - shalin - 2016-11-02 19:52:42",
  "startTime": "2017-01-02T06:19:15.192Z",
  "uptime": "0 days, 0 hours, 4 minutes, 50 seconds",
  "memory": "29.5 MB (%6) of 490.7 MB",
  "cloud": {
    "ZooKeeper": "localhost:9983",
    "liveNodes": "2",
    "collections": "1"}
}

Solr process 13400 running on port 7574
{
  "solr_home": "/home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/example/cloud/node2/solr",
  "version": "6.3.0 a66a44513ee8191e25b477372094bfa846450316 - shalin - 2016-11-02 19:52:42",
  "startTime": "2017-01-02T06:19:34.399Z",
  "uptime": "0 days, 0 hours, 4 minutes, 32 seconds",
  "memory": "105.7 MB (%21.5) of 490.7 MB",
  "cloud": {
    "ZooKeeper": "localhost:9983",
    "liveNodes": "2",
    "collections": "1"}
}
```

This will gather all the Solr instances running on the system and provide basic information about them, such as the version and memory usage.

11. Stopping All Solr Instances

We can use -all parameter to stop all running Solr instances.

```
$ bin/solr stop -all
```


The image shows a terminal window titled 'Terminal' with the following content:

```
File Edit View Search Terminal Help
[rakesh@localhost bin]$ ./solr stop -all
Sending stop command to Solr running on port 8983 ... waiting up to 180 seconds to allow Jetty process 13135 to stop gracefully.
Sending stop command to Solr running on port 7574 ... waiting up to 180 seconds to allow Jetty process 13400 to stop gracefully.
[rakesh@localhost bin]$
```

The terminal window is part of a desktop environment. The top bar shows 'Applications', 'Places', and 'Terminal'. The system clock indicates 'Mon 11:56 AM'. The terminal title bar shows 'rakesh@localhost:~/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/bin'. The bottom taskbar shows several open windows: 'solr in cloud mode - priyanka.suri...', 'example', 'rakesh@localhost:~/Desktop/solr...', and 'Solr cloud mode(embedded zk)'. The system tray shows '1 / 4' and a help icon.

3. Starting Solr in Cloud Mode with Embedded Zookeeper: Interactive Script Method

SolrCloud is designed to provide a fault tolerant, scalable and highly available environment for created web application that can index the data for searching. This can be done by distributing your indexed content at different servers and querying user's requests across those multiple servers.

Your information is indexed and stored in "collections" which is then distributed to a group of machines that work together to provide storage and search results which is called a SolrCloud Cluster.

An embedded Zookeeper server is also bundled with Solr that helps to manage the overall structure so that both indexing and search requests can be routed properly.

1.Starting SolrCloud

To launch Solr in Cloud mode with an embedded Zookeeper run the following command:

```
$bin/solr -e cloud
```


This starts an interactive session which takes us through the easy steps of setting up a simple SolrCloud cluster with embedded Zookeeper. All of the defaults will be fine.

Now, we have to give two port numbers to the created nodes for our SolrCloud cluster.


```
Applications ▾ Places ▾ Terminal ▾ Sat 1:43 PM [Icons] [Power]
rakesh@localhost:~/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/bin

File Edit View Search Terminal Help

This interactive session will help you launch a SolrCloud cluster on your local workstation.
To begin, how many Solr nodes would you like to run in your local cluster? (specify 1-4 nodes) [2]:
2
Ok, let's start up 2 Solr nodes for your example SolrCloud cluster.
Please enter the port for node1 [8983]:
8983
Please enter the port for node2 [7574]:
7574
Solr home directory /home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/example/cloud/node1/solr already exists.
/home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/example/cloud/node2 already exists.

Starting up Solr on port 8983 using command:
/home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/bin/solr start -cloud -p 8983 -s "/home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/example/cloud/node1/solr" -m 2g

Archiving 1 old GC log files to /home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/example/cloud/node1/solr/../logs/archived
Archiving 1 console log files to /home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/example/cloud/node1/solr/../logs/archived
Rotating solr logs, keeping a max of 9 generations
Waiting up to 180 seconds to see Solr running on port 8983 [ ]
Started Solr server on port 8983 (pid=18648). Happy searching!

Starting up Solr on port 7574 using command:
/home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/bin/solr start -cloud -p 7574 -s "/home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/example/cloud/node2/solr" -z localhost:9983 -m 2g

Archiving 1 old GC log files to /home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/example/cloud/node2/solr/../logs/archived
Archiving 1 console log files to /home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/example/cloud/node2/solr/../logs/archived
Rotating solr logs, keeping a max of 9 generations
[ ]
```

We can provide the name to create a new collection or choose to use the previously created collection.


```
Applications ▾ Places ▾ Terminal ▾ Sat 1:44 PM [Icons] [Power]
rakesh@localhost:~/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/bin

File Edit View Search Terminal Help

8983
Please enter the port for node2 [7574]:
7574
Solr home directory /home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/example/cloud/node1/solr already exists.
/home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/example/cloud/node2 already exists.

Starting up Solr on port 8983 using command:
/home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/bin/solr start -cloud -p 8983 -s "/home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/example/cloud/node1/solr" -m 2g

Archiving 1 old GC log files to /home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/example/cloud/node1/solr/../logs/archived
Archiving 1 console log files to /home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/example/cloud/node1/solr/../logs/archived
Rotating solr logs, keeping a max of 9 generations
Waiting up to 180 seconds to see Solr running on port 8983 [ ]
Started Solr server on port 8983 (pid=18648). Happy searching!

Starting up Solr on port 7574 using command:
/home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/bin/solr start -cloud -p 7574 -s "/home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/example/cloud/node2/solr" -z localhost:9983 -m 2g

Archiving 1 old GC log files to /home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/example/cloud/node2/solr/../logs/archived
Archiving 1 console log files to /home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/example/cloud/node2/solr/../logs/archived
Rotating solr logs, keeping a max of 9 generations
Waiting up to 180 seconds to see Solr running on port 7574 [-]
Started Solr server on port 7574 (pid=19042). Happy searching!

Now let's create a new collection for indexing documents in your 2-node cluster.
Please provide a name for your new collection: [gettingstarted]
Collection1[ ]
```

```
Applications Places Terminal Sat 1:47 PM
rakesh@localhost:~/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/bin

File Edit View Search Terminal Help
WARN - 2016-12-31 13:45:41.532; org.apache.solr.common.cloud.ConnectionManager; Watcher org.apache.solr.common.cloud.ConnectionManager@9ca07b1 name:
ZooKeeperConnection Watcher:localhost:9983 got event WatchedEvent state:Disconnected type:None path:null path: null type: None
WARN - 2016-12-31 13:45:43.501; org.apache.solr.common.cloud.ConnectionManager; zkClient has disconnected
{
  "responseHeader":{
    "status":0,
    "QTime":107426},
  "success":{
    "192.168.1.16:8983_solr":{
      "responseHeader":{
        "status":0,
        "QTime":105908},
      "core":"Collection1_shard1_replica2"},
    "192.168.1.16:7574_solr":{
      "responseHeader":{
        "status":0,
        "QTime":105909},
      "core":"Collection1_shard1_replica1"}}}

Enabling auto soft-commits with maxTime 3 secs using the Config API

POSTing request to Config API: http://localhost:8983/solr/Collection1/config
{"set-property":{"updateHandler.autoSoftCommit.maxTime":"3000"}}
Successfully set-property updateHandler.autoSoftCommit.maxTime to 3000

SolrCloud example running, please visit: http://localhost:8983/solr

[rakesh@localhost bin]$
```

You can visit <http://localhost:8983/solr> to check the status of SolrCloud.

The screenshot shows the Solr Admin web interface. The browser address bar displays `localhost:8983/solr/#/`. The page features a sidebar with navigation options: Dashboard, Logging, Cloud, Collections, Java Properties, and Thread Dump. The main content area is divided into several sections:

- Instance:** Shows the instance started 9 minutes ago.
- Versions:** Lists installed versions:

Component	Version	Checksum	Path	Author	Date
solr-spec	6.3.0				
solr-impl	6.3.0	a66a44513ee8191e25b477372094bfa846450316	-	shalin	2016-11-02
lucene-spec	6.3.0				
lucene-impl	6.3.0	a66a44513ee8191e25b477372094bfa846450316	-	shalin	2016-11-02
- JVM:** Shows runtime information: Oracle Corporation Java HotSpot(TM) 64-Bit Server VM 1.8.0_66 25.66-b17 and 1 processor.
- System:** Displays resource usage with progress bars:

Resource	Usage	Max
Physical Memory	96.0%	1.78 GB
Swap Space	13.0%	3.62 GB
File Descriptor Count	5.5%	4096
JVM-Memory	10.5%	

After logging into SolrCloud GUI, we can check the number of shards and replicas created in the Graph section.

2. Posting Documents in a Collection

We can post the documents to be indexed into your collection by giving following command,

```
$. /bin/post -c Collection1 example/exampledocs/*.xml
```



```
rakesh@localhost:~/Desktop/solr-6.3.0
File Edit View Search Terminal Help
[rakesh@localhost bin]$ cd ..
[rakesh@localhost solr-6.3.0]$ ./bin/post -c Collection1 example/exampledocs/*.xml
/usr/java/jdk1.8.0_66/bin/java -classpath /home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/dist/solr-core-6.3.0.jar -Dauto=yes -Dc=Collection1 -Ddata=files org.apache.solr.util.SimplePostTool example/exampledocs/gb18030-example.xml example/exampledocs/hd.xml example/exampledocs/ipod_other.xml example/exampledocs/ipod_video.xml example/exampledocs/manufacturers.xml example/exampledocs/mem.xml example/exampledocs/money.xml example/exampledocs/monitor2.xml example/exampledocs/monitor.xml example/exampledocs/mp500.xml example/exampledocs/sd500.xml example/exampledocs/solr.xml example/exampledocs/utf8-example.xml example/exampledocs/vidcard.xml
SimplePostTool version 5.0.0
Posting files to [base] url http://localhost:8983/solr/Collection1/update...
Entering auto mode. File endings considered are xml,json,jsonl,csv,pdf,doc,docx,ppt,pptx,xls,xlsx,odt,odp,ods,ott,otp,ots,rtf,htm,html,txt,log
POSTing file gb18030-example.xml (application/xml) to [base]
POSTing file hd.xml (application/xml) to [base]
POSTing file ipod_other.xml (application/xml) to [base]
POSTing file ipod_video.xml (application/xml) to [base]
POSTing file manufacturers.xml (application/xml) to [base]
POSTing file mem.xml (application/xml) to [base]
POSTing file money.xml (application/xml) to [base]
POSTing file monitor2.xml (application/xml) to [base]
POSTing file monitor.xml (application/xml) to [base]
POSTing file mp500.xml (application/xml) to [base]
POSTing file sd500.xml (application/xml) to [base]
POSTing file solr.xml (application/xml) to [base]
POSTing file utf8-example.xml (application/xml) to [base]
POSTing file vidcard.xml (application/xml) to [base]
14 files indexed.
COMMITting Solr index changes to http://localhost:8983/solr/Collection1/update...
Time spent: 0:02:31.892
[rakesh@localhost solr-6.3.0]$
```


The screenshot shows the Solr Admin web interface in a Mozilla Firefox browser. The address bar shows `localhost:8983/solr/#/Collection1/collection-overview`. The page title is "Solr Admin - Mozilla Firefox".

The main content area displays the "Collection: Collection1" overview. On the left, there is a sidebar with navigation options: Dashboard, Logging, Cloud, Collections, Java Properties, Thread Dump, and a dropdown menu for "Collection1".

The "Collection: Collection1" section shows the following configuration:

- Config name: Collection1
- Max shards per node: 2
- Replication factor: 2
- Auto-add replicas: ✘
- Router name: compositeld

On the right, the "Shards" section shows two shards:

- shard1**: Range: 80000000-fffffff, Active: ✔, Replicas: Collection1_shard1_replica2, Collection1_shard1_replica1
- shard2**: Range: 0-7fffffff, Active: ✔, Replicas: Collection1_shard2_replica2, Collection1_shard2_replica1

The bottom of the browser window shows the taskbar with icons for Pictures, configsets, Screenshot from 2016-12-31..., rakesh@localhost:~/Desktop/sol..., and Solr Admin - Mozilla Firefox. The system tray shows the time as 1 / 4.

3. Running Query on the Documents

We can query the documents in our collection by giving input in -q parameter.

After running the query we will get the results in the form of fields as described in the chosen configuration or schema.

Applications ▾ Places ▾ Firefox Web Browser ▾ Sat 2:00 PM

Solr Admin - Mozilla Firefox

Solr Admin x M Inbox (2,153) - priya... x

localhost:8983/solr/#/Collection1/query

Dataimport Documents Files Query Stream Schema

Core Selector ▾

df

Raw Query Parameters
key1=val1&key2=val2

wt
json

indent
 debugQuery

dismax
 edismax
 hl
 facet
 spatial
 spellcheck

Execute Query

```

    "This is a feature (translated)",
    "这份文件是很有光泽",
    "This document is very shiny (translated)",
    "price": [0.0],
    "inStock": [true],
    "_version_": 1555219251217825792},
  {
    "id": "IW-02",
    "name": ["iPod & iPod Mini USB 2.0 Cable"],
    "manu": ["Belkin"],
    "manu_id_s": "belkin",
    "cat": ["electronics",
    "connector"],
    "features": ["car power adapter for iPod, white"],
    "weight": [2.0],
    "price": [11.5],
    "popularity": [1],
    "inStock": [false],
    "store": [{"37.7752, -122.4232}],
    "manufacturedate_dt": "2006-02-14T23:55:59Z",
    "_version_": 1555219359349080064},
  {
    "id": "MA147LL/A",
    "name": ["Apple 60 GB iPod with Video Playback Black"],
    "manu": ["Apple Computer Inc."],
    "manu_id_s": "apple",

```

Pictures configsets Screenshot from 2016-12-31 ... rakesh@localhost:~/Desktop/sol... Solr Admin - Mozilla Firefox 1 / 4

Applications ▾ Places ▾ Firefox Web Browser ▾ Sat 2:00 PM

Solr Admin - Mozilla Firefox

Solr Admin x M Inbox (2,153) - priya... x

localhost:8983/solr/#/Collection1/query

```

    "2.5-inch, 320x240 color TFT LCD display with LED backlight",
    "Up to 20 hours of battery life",
    "Plays AAC, MP3, WAV, AIFF, Audible, Apple Lossless, H.264 video",
    "Notes, Calendar, Phone book, Hold button, Date display, Photo wallet, Built-in games, JPEG photo playback, Upgrade",
    "includes": ["earbud headphones, USB cable"],
    "weight": [5.5],
    "price": [399.0],
    "popularity": [10],
    "inStock": [true],
    "store": [{"37.7752, -100.0232}],
    "manufacturedate_dt": "2005-10-12T08:00:00Z",
    "_version_": 1555219380331085824},
  {
    "id": "adata",
    "compName_s": "A-Data Technology",
    "address_s": "46221 Landing Parkway Fremont, CA 94538",
    "_version_": 1555219385887490048},
  {
    "id": "asus",
    "compName_s": "ASUS Computer",
    "address_s": "800 Corporate Way Fremont, CA 94539",
    "_version_": 1555219395321528320},
  {
    "id": "belkin",
    "compName_s": "Belkin",
    "address_s": "12045 E. Waterfront Drive Playa Vista, CA 90094",

```

Pictures configsets Screenshot from 2016-12-31 ... rakesh@localhost:~/Desktop/sol... Solr Admin - Mozilla Firefox 1 / 4

4. Getting started with External Apache ZooKeeper 3.4.6: Download & Installation

ZooKeeper is an open source Apache™ project which provides a centralized infrastructure and services that enable synchronization across a cluster. ZooKeeper maintains common objects needed in large cluster environments. Examples of these objects include configuration information, hierarchical naming space, and so on. Applications can leverage these services to coordinate distributed processing across large clusters.

Following services provided by Apache ZooKeeper makes it compatible with Apache Solr to provide benefits in the distributed computing environment.

- **Naming service** – Identifying the nodes in a cluster by name. It is similar to DNS, but for nodes.
- **Configuration management** – Latest and up-to-date configuration information of the system for a joining node.
- **Cluster management** – Joining / leaving of a node in a cluster and node status at real time.
- **Leader election** – Electing a node as leader for coordination purpose.
- **Locking and synchronization service** – Locking the data while modifying it. This mechanism helps you in automatic fail recovery while connecting other distributed applications like Apache HBase.
- **Highly reliable data registry** – Availability of data even when one or a few nodes are down.

This section covers the following topics,

- Downloading Zookeeper 3.4.6
- Installing Zookeeper 3.4.6

1. Downloading Zookeeper 3.4.6

We can download the current stable version of ZooKeeper from any of the www.apache.org mirror website.

<http://ftp.jaist.ac.jp/pub/apache/zookeeper/>

The screenshot shows a Firefox browser window with the address bar set to <http://ftp.jaist.ac.jp/pub/apache/zookeeper/>. The page title is "Index of /pub/apache/zookeeper - Mozilla Firefox". The main heading is "ZooKeeper Releases". Below the heading, there is a notice: "Please make sure you're downloading from a [nearby mirror site](#), not from www.apache.org. We suggest downloading the current [stable](#) release. Older releases are available from the [archives](#)." Below this notice is a table listing various ZooKeeper releases.

Name	Last modified	Size	Description
Parent Directory	-	-	-
zookeeper/	2015-10-15 01:15	-	-
current/	2016-09-03 13:28	-	-
stable/	2016-09-03 13:28	-	-
zookeeper-3.3.6/	2015-10-15 01:15	-	-
zookeeper-3.4.6/	2016-01-11 02:11	-	-
zookeeper-3.4.8/	2016-02-21 05:41	-	-
zookeeper-3.4.9/	2016-09-03 13:28	-	-
zookeeper-3.5.0-alpha/	2015-10-15 01:16	-	-
zookeeper-3.5.1-alpha/	2015-10-15 01:15	-	-
zookeeper-3.5.2-alpha/	2016-07-21 02:09	-	-

The screenshot shows a Firefox browser window with the address bar set to <http://ftp.jaist.ac.jp/pub/apache/zookeeper/zookeeper-3.4.6/>. The page title is "Index of /pub/apache/zookeeper/zookeeper-3.4.6 - Mozilla Firefox". The main heading is "Index of /pub/apache/zookeeper/zookeeper-3.4.6". Below the heading is a table listing the files in the directory.

Name	Last modified	Size	Description
Parent Directory	-	-	-
zookeeper-3.4.6.tar.gz	2016-01-11 02:11	17M	-

Apache/2.4.25 (Unix) OpenSSL/1.0.2j-fips Server at ftp.jaist.ac.jp Port 80

The screenshot shows a Firefox browser window with the address bar set to <http://ftp.jaist.ac.jp/pub/apache/zookeeper/zookeeper-3.4.6/zookeeper-3.4.6.tar.gz>. The page title is "Index of /pub/apache/zookeeper/zookeeper-3.4.6 - Mozilla Firefox". The main heading is "Index of /pub/apache/zookeeper/zookeeper-3.4.6". Below the heading is a table listing the files in the directory.

Name	Last modified	Size	Description
Parent Directory	-	-	-
zookeeper-3.4.6.tar.gz	2016-01-11 02:11	17M	-

2. Installing Zookeeper 3.4.6

Once finished with downloading Zookeeper we can move on to the installation step.

Now, extract the downloaded ZooKeeper-3.4.6.tar.gz file on the system to start with ZooKeeper services.

Now, let's move into the conf directory in the extracted Zookeeper folder.

Make a copy of the zoo_sample.cfg file present in the conf directory and rename it as zoo.cfg file.

Now, let's make the required changes in the zoo.cfg file as required in the next section.

5. Starting Solr in Cloud Mode with External Zookeeper Ensemble on a Single Machine.

“Cloud” became very ambiguous term and it can mean virtually anything those days. Think about Solr Cloud as one logical service hosted on multiple servers. In SolrCloud we can have multiple collections. Collections can be divided into partitions which can be referred as slices. Each slice can exist in multiple copies, these copies of the same slice are called shards. One of the shards within a slice is the leader, though this is not fixed. Any shard can become the leader through a leader-election process.

SolrCloud provides replicas for providing redundancy for both scalability and fault tolerance.

Zookeeper is a centralized service for maintaining configuration information, naming, providing distributed synchronization, and providing group services. A Zookeeper server helps to manage the overall structure so that both indexing and search requests can be routed properly.

1. Creating a Zookeeper Cluster on the Same System

To create a cluster of Zookeeper on the system, create three copies of the extracted ZooKeeper folder and name them as ZooKeeper1, ZooKeeper2 and Zookeeper3.

Now we will arrange a cluster of three nodes on the same host. Below is the cluster map:

Node 1: /Home/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper1/

Node 2: /Home/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper2/

Node 3: /Home/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper3/

Store the created folders ZooKeeper1, ZooKeeper2 and ZooKeeper3 under a directory named as ZooKeeper.

After creating multiple copies of ZooKeeper, let's create a data directory to store the data and log files for Zookeeper ensemble.

Now, create three Zookeeper data directories to store data and log files for three individual ZooKeeper ensembles and name it as zook1, zook2 and zook3.

Now, let's make the required changes in the zoo.cfg file for the Node1.

tickTime=2000

initLimit=10

syncLimit=5

dataDir=/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookdata/zook1

clientPort=2181

server.1=localhost:2666:3666

server.2=localhost:2667:3667

server.3=localhost:2668:3668

The screenshot shows a gedit text editor window titled 'zoo.cfg' with the file path '~/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper1/conf'. The window contains the following configuration text:

```
# synchronization phase can take
initLimit=10
# The number of ticks that can pass between
# sending a request and getting an acknowledgement
syncLimit=5
# the directory where the snapshot is stored.
# do not use /tmp for storage, /tmp here is just
# example sakes.
dataDir=/home/rakesh/Desktop/zoo_data/z1
# the port at which the clients will connect
clientPort=2181
# the maximum number of client connections.
# increase this if you need to handle more clients
#maxClientCnxns=60
#
# Be sure to read the maintenance section of the
# administrator guide before turning on autopurge.
#
# http://zookeeper.apache.org/doc/current/zookeeperAdmin.html#sc_maintenance
#
# The number of snapshots to retain in dataDir
#autopurge.snapRetainCount=3
# Purge task interval in hours
# Set to "0" to disable auto purge feature
#autopurge.purgeInterval=1
server.1=localhost:2666:3666
server.2=localhost:2667:3667
server.3=localhost:2668:3668
```

The window's status bar at the bottom shows 'Plain Text', 'Tab Width: 8', 'Ln 8, Col 12', and 'INS'. The taskbar at the very bottom displays several open applications: 'Inbox (2,165) - priyanka.suri27...', 'rakesh@localhost:~/Desktop/sol...', '[apache-sol-ref-guide-6.0.pdf]', 'Zookeeper dl', and 'zoo.cfg (~/Desktop/zookeeper/z... 1 / 4)'.

Here is the required changes in the zoo.cfg file for the Node2.

tickTime=2000

initLimit=10

syncLimit=5

dataDir=/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookdata/zook2

clientPort=2182

server.1=localhost:2666:3666

server.2=localhost:2667:3667

server.3=localhost:2668:3668

The screenshot shows a gedit text editor window titled 'zoo.cfg' with the file path '~/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper2/conf'. The editor contains the following configuration text:

```
# The number of milliseconds of each tick
tickTime=2000
# The number of ticks that the initial
# synchronization phase can take
initLimit=10
# The number of ticks that can pass between
# sending a request and getting an acknowledgement
syncLimit=5
# the directory where the snapshot is stored.
# do not use /tmp for storage, /tmp here is just
# example sakes.
dataDir=/home/rakesh/Desktop/zoo_data/z1
# the port at which the clients will connect
clientPort=2181
# the maximum number of client connections.
# increase this if you need to handle more clients
#maxClientCnxns=60
#
# Be sure to read the maintenance section of the
# administrator guide before turning on autopurge.
#
# http://zookeeper.apache.org/doc/current/zookeeperAdmin.html#sc_maintenance
#
# The number of snapshots to retain in dataDir
#autopurge.snapRetainCount=3
# Purge task interval in hours
# Set to "0" to disable auto purge feature
#autopurge.purgeInterval=1
server.1=localhost:2666:3666
server.2=localhost:2667:3667
```

The editor's status bar at the bottom shows 'Plain Text', 'Tab Width: 8', 'Ln 14, Col 16', and 'INS'. The taskbar at the bottom includes an 'Inbox (2,165) - priyanka.suri27...' window, a terminal window 'rakesh@localhost:~/Desktop/sol...', a PDF viewer '[apache-sol-ref-guide-6.0.pdf]', a 'conf' folder icon, and the active 'zoo.cfg (~/Desktop/zookeeper/z...' window with '1 / 4' lines.

Here is the required changes in the zoo.cfg file for the Node3.

tickTime=2000

initLimit=10

syncLimit=5

dataDir=/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookdata/zook3

clientPort=2183

server.1=localhost:2666:3666

server.2=localhost:2667:3667

server.3=localhost:2668:3668

The screenshot shows a gedit text editor window titled '*zoo.cfg' with the file path '~/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper3/conf'. The window contains the following configuration text:

```
# synchronization phase can take
initLimit=10
# The number of ticks that can pass between
# sending a request and getting an acknowledgement
syncLimit=5
# the directory where the snapshot is stored.
# do not use /tmp for storage, /tmp here is just
# example sakes.
dataDir=/home/rakesh/Desktop/zoo_data/z1
# the port at which the clients will connect
clientPort=2183
# the maximum number of client connections.
# increase this if you need to handle more clients
#maxClientCnxns=60
#
# Be sure to read the maintenance section of the
# administrator guide before turning on autopurge.
#
# http://zookeeper.apache.org/doc/current/zookeeperAdmin.html#sc_maintenance
#
# The number of snapshots to retain in dataDir
#autopurge.snapRetainCount=3
# Purge task interval in hours
# Set to "0" to disable auto purge feature
#autopurge.purgeInterval=1
server.1=localhost:2666:3666
server.2=localhost:2667:3667
server.3=localhost:2668:3668
```

The window's status bar at the bottom shows 'Plain Text', 'Tab Width: 8', 'Ln 14, Col 12', and 'INS'. The taskbar at the bottom of the screen shows several open applications, including an inbox, a terminal window for 'rakesh@localhost', a PDF viewer for 'apache-solr-ref-guide-6.0.pdf', a 'conf' file, and the current '*zoo.cfg' file.

Server.n specifies the **address and port numbers** used by ZooKeeper Server n.

Now, let's understand in detail the fields specified on the right side of Server.n

- **The hostname or IP address** of server n is specified in the first field.
- The **port used for peer to peer communication** in the Quorum (connecting followers to leaders) is specified in the second field. The TCP connection to the leader is initiated by the follower using this port.
- The third field specifies a **port for leader election** in the Quorum.

Since we are using multiple Servers, the server figures out its ID by accessing a file named myid in the data directory created by the user in the zoo.cfg file.

The myid file can be created with the following command for Server1, Server2 and Server3 in the data directory.

```
$ echo 1 > /home/rakesh/Desktop/zookdata/zook1/myid
```

```
$ echo 2 > /home/rakesh/Desktop/zookdata/zook2/myid
```

```
$ echo 3 > /home/rakesh/Desktop/zookdata/zook3/myid
```

2.Starting Zookeeper in a Quorum

Now, let's start the ZooKeeper instances using the following commands:

```
$ zookeeper/zookeeper1/bin/zkServer.sh start zoo.cfg
```

```
$ zookeeper/zookeeper1/bin/zkServer.sh start zoo.cfg
```

```
$ zookeeper/zookeeper1/bin/zkServer.sh start zoo.cfg
```



```
rakesh@localhost:~/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper3/bin
File Edit View Search Terminal Help
[rakesh@localhost ~]$ cd Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper1/bin
[rakesh@localhost bin]$ ./zkServer.sh start zoo.cfg
JMX enabled by default
Using config: /home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper1/bin/../conf/zoo.cfg
Starting zookeeper ... STARTED
[rakesh@localhost bin]$ cd ~/Desktop
[rakesh@localhost Desktop]$ cd zookeeper/zookeeper2/bin
[rakesh@localhost bin]$ ./zkServer.sh start zoo.cfg
JMX enabled by default
Using config: /home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper2/bin/../conf/zoo.cfg
Starting zookeeper ... STARTED
[rakesh@localhost bin]$ cd ~/Desktop
[rakesh@localhost Desktop]$ cd zookeeper/zookeeper3/bin
[rakesh@localhost bin]$ ./zkServer.sh start zoo.cfg
JMX enabled by default
Using config: /home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper3/bin/../conf/zoo.cfg
Starting zookeeper ... STARTED
[rakesh@localhost bin]$
```

The screenshot shows a terminal window with the following content: Applications, Places, Terminal, Mon 4:59 PM, rakesh@localhost:~/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper3/bin, File Edit View Search Terminal Help, [rakesh@localhost ~]\$ cd Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper1/bin, [rakesh@localhost bin]\$./zkServer.sh start zoo.cfg, JMX enabled by default, Using config: /home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper1/bin/../conf/zoo.cfg, Starting zookeeper ... STARTED, [rakesh@localhost bin]\$ cd ~/Desktop, [rakesh@localhost Desktop]\$ cd zookeeper/zookeeper2/bin, [rakesh@localhost bin]\$./zkServer.sh start zoo.cfg, JMX enabled by default, Using config: /home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper2/bin/../conf/zoo.cfg, Starting zookeeper ... STARTED, [rakesh@localhost bin]\$ cd ~/Desktop, [rakesh@localhost Desktop]\$ cd zookeeper/zookeeper3/bin, [rakesh@localhost bin]\$./zkServer.sh start zoo.cfg, JMX enabled by default, Using config: /home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper3/bin/../conf/zoo.cfg, Starting zookeeper ... STARTED, [rakesh@localhost bin]\$

Multiple Zookeepers on Single Sys... rakesh@localhost:~/Desktop/zoo... apache-sol-ref-guide-6.0.pdf conf 1 / 4

After starting the ZooKeeper instances, let's check the status of the individual ZooKeeper instances step by step using the command,

`$ zookeeper/zookeeper1/bin/zkServer.sh status`


```
rakesh@localhost:~/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper1/bin
File Edit View Search Terminal Help
[rakesh@localhost bin]$ ./zkServer.sh status
JMX enabled by default
Using config: /home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper3/bin/./conf/zoo.cfg
Mode: follower
[rakesh@localhost bin]$ cd ~/Desktop
[rakesh@localhost Desktop]$ cd zookeeper/zookeeper2/bin
[rakesh@localhost bin]$ ./zkServer.sh status
JMX enabled by default
Using config: /home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper2/bin/./conf/zoo.cfg
Mode: leader
[rakesh@localhost bin]$ cd ~/Desktop
[rakesh@localhost Desktop]$ cd zookeeper/zookeeper1/bin
[rakesh@localhost bin]$ ./zkServer.sh status
JMX enabled by default
Using config: /home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper1/bin/./conf/zoo.cfg
Mode: follower
[rakesh@localhost bin]$
```

After running the status command for ZooKeeper ensemble, we can check the followers and leader association among them.

Here, the association is given as follows:

Zookeeper1 as follower

Zookeeper2 as leader

Zookeeper3 as follower

3.Starting Zookeeper Client

- Now, let's start the ZooKeeper1 Client instance using the command:

```
$ zookeeper/zookeeper1/bin/zkCli.sh -server localhost:2184
```



```
rakesh@localhost:~/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper1/bin
File Edit View Search Terminal Help
[rakesh@localhost bin]$ ./zkCli.sh -server localhost:2184
Connecting to localhost:2184
2017-01-03 10:03:11,846 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:zookeeper.version=3.4.6-1569965, built on 02/20/2014 09:09 GMT
2017-01-03 10:03:12,026 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:host.name=localhost
2017-01-03 10:03:12,026 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:java.version=1.8.0_66
2017-01-03 10:03:12,216 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:java.vendor=Oracle Corporation
2017-01-03 10:03:12,216 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:java.home=/usr/java/jdk1.8.0_66/jre
2017-01-03 10:03:12,216 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:java.class.path=/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper1/bin/./build/classes:/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper1/bin/./build/lib/*:jar:/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper1/bin/./lib/slf4j-log4j12-1.6.1.jar:/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper1/bin/./lib/slf4j-api-1.6.1.jar:/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper1/bin/./lib/netty-3.7.0.Final.jar:/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper1/bin/./lib/log4j-1.2.16.jar:/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper1/bin/./lib/jline-0.9.94.jar:/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper1/bin/./zookeeper-3.4.6.jar:/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper1/bin/./src/java/lib/*.jar:/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper1/bin/./conf:
2017-01-03 10:03:12,216 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:java.library.path=/usr/java/packages/lib/amd64:/usr/lib64:/lib64:/lib:/usr/lib
2017-01-03 10:03:12,216 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:java.io.tmpdir=/tmp
2017-01-03 10:03:12,216 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:java.compiler=<NA>
2017-01-03 10:03:12,216 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:os.name=Linux
2017-01-03 10:03:12,216 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:os.arch=amd64
2017-01-03 10:03:12,216 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:os.version=3.10.0-327.4.5.el7.x86_64
2017-01-03 10:03:12,216 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:user.name=rakesh
2017-01-03 10:03:12,217 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:user.home=/home/rakesh
2017-01-03 10:03:12,217 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:user.dir=/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper1/bin
2017-01-03 10:03:12,218 [myid:] - INFO [main:ZooKeeper@438] - Initiating client connection, connectString=localhost:2184 sessionTimeout=30000 watcher=org.apache.zookeeper.ZooKeeperMain$MyWatcher@506c589e
Welcome to ZooKeeper!
JLine support is enabled
2017-01-03 10:03:16,249 [myid:] - INFO [main-SendThread(localhost:2184):ClientCnxn$SendThread@975] - Opening socket connection to server localhost/127.0.0.1:2184. Will not attempt to authenticate using SASL (unknown error)
```



```
rakesh@localhost:~/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper1/bin
File Edit View Search Terminal Help
:/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper1/bin/./zookeeper-3.4.6.jar:/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper1/bin/./src/java/lib/*.jar:/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper1/bin/./conf:
2017-01-03 10:03:12,216 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:java.library.path=/usr/java/packages/lib/amd64:/usr/lib64:/lib64:/lib:/usr/lib
2017-01-03 10:03:12,216 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:java.io.tmpdir=/tmp
2017-01-03 10:03:12,216 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:java.compiler=<NA>
2017-01-03 10:03:12,216 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:os.name=Linux
2017-01-03 10:03:12,216 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:os.arch=amd64
2017-01-03 10:03:12,216 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:os.version=3.10.0-327.4.5.el7.x86_64
2017-01-03 10:03:12,216 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:user.name=rakesh
2017-01-03 10:03:12,217 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:user.home=/home/rakesh
2017-01-03 10:03:12,217 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:user.dir=/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper1/bin
2017-01-03 10:03:12,218 [myid:] - INFO [main:ZooKeeper@438] - Initiating client connection, connectString=localhost:2184 sessionTimeout=30000 watcher=org.apache.zookeeper.ZooKeeperMain$MyWatcher@506c589e
Welcome to ZooKeeper!
JLine support is enabled
2017-01-03 10:03:16,249 [myid:] - INFO [main-SendThread(localhost:2184):ClientCnxn$SendThread@975] - Opening socket connection to server localhost/127.0.0.1:2184. Will not attempt to authenticate using SASL (unknown error)
2017-01-03 10:03:16,503 [myid:] - INFO [main-SendThread(localhost:2184):ClientCnxn$SendThread@852] - Socket connection established to localhost/127.0.0.1:2184, initiating session
[zk: localhost:2184(CONNECTING) 0] 2017-01-03 10:03:17,018 [myid:] - INFO [main-SendThread(localhost:2184):ClientCnxn$SendThread@1235] - Session establishment complete on server localhost/127.0.0.1:2184, sessionId = 0x1595efcc8600000, negotiated timeout = 30000

WATCHER::

WatchedEvent state:SyncConnected type:None path:null
ls /
[zookeeper]
[zk: localhost:2184(CONNECTED) 1] □
```

➤ Here is the ZooKeeper2 Client instance running using the command:

```
$ zookeeper/zookeeper2/bin/zkCli.sh -server localhost:2182
```



```
rakesh@localhost:~/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper2/bin
File Edit View Search Terminal Help
[rakesh@localhost bin]$ ./zkCli.sh -server localhost:2182
Connecting to localhost:2182
2017-01-03 10:04:46,158 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:zookeeper.version=3.4.6-1569965, built on 02/20/2014 09:09 GMT
2017-01-03 10:04:46,212 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:host.name=localhost
2017-01-03 10:04:46,212 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:java.version=1.8.0_66
2017-01-03 10:04:46,307 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:java.vendor=Oracle Corporation
2017-01-03 10:04:46,307 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:java.home=/usr/java/jdk1.8.0_66/jre
2017-01-03 10:04:46,307 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:java.class.path=/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper2/bin/./build/classes:/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper2/bin/./build/lib/*:jar:/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper2/bin/./lib/slf4j-log4j12-1.6.1.jar:/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper2/bin/./lib/slf4j-api-1.6.1.jar:/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper2/bin/./lib/netty-3.7.0.Final.jar:/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper2/bin/./lib/log4j-1.2.16.jar:/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper2/bin/./lib/jline-0.9.94.jar:/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper2/bin/./zookeeper-3.4.6.jar:/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper2/bin/./src/java/lib/*:jar:/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper2/bin/./conf:
2017-01-03 10:04:46,308 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:java.library.path=/usr/java/packages/lib/amd64:/usr/lib64:/lib64:/lib:/usr/lib
2017-01-03 10:04:46,308 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:java.io.tmpdir=/tmp
2017-01-03 10:04:46,308 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:java.compiler=<NA>
2017-01-03 10:04:46,308 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:os.name=Linux
2017-01-03 10:04:46,308 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:os.arch=amd64
2017-01-03 10:04:46,308 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:os.version=3.10.0-327.4.5.el7.x86_64
2017-01-03 10:04:46,308 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:user.name=rakesh
2017-01-03 10:04:46,308 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:user.home=/home/rakesh
2017-01-03 10:04:46,308 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:user.dir=/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper2/bin
2017-01-03 10:04:46,309 [myid:] - INFO [main:ZooKeeper@438] - Initiating client connection, connectString=localhost:2182 sessionTimeout=30000 watcher=org.apache.zookeeper.ZooKeeperMain$MyWatcher@506c589e
Welcome to ZooKeeper!
2017-01-03 10:04:47,159 [myid:] - INFO [main-SendThread(localhost:2182):ClientCnxn$SendThread@975] - Opening socket connection to server localhost/0:0:0:0:0:0:0:1:2182. Will not attempt to authenticate using SASL (unknown error)
JLine support is enabled
```



```
rakesh@localhost:~/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper2/bin
File Edit View Search Terminal Help
:/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper2/bin/./zookeeper-3.4.6.jar:/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper2/bin/./src/java/lib/*:jar:/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper2/bin/./conf:
2017-01-03 10:04:46,308 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:java.library.path=/usr/java/packages/lib/amd64:/usr/lib64:/lib64:/lib:/usr/lib
2017-01-03 10:04:46,308 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:java.io.tmpdir=/tmp
2017-01-03 10:04:46,308 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:java.compiler=<NA>
2017-01-03 10:04:46,308 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:os.name=Linux
2017-01-03 10:04:46,308 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:os.arch=amd64
2017-01-03 10:04:46,308 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:os.version=3.10.0-327.4.5.el7.x86_64
2017-01-03 10:04:46,308 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:user.name=rakesh
2017-01-03 10:04:46,308 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:user.home=/home/rakesh
2017-01-03 10:04:46,308 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:user.dir=/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper2/bin
2017-01-03 10:04:46,309 [myid:] - INFO [main:ZooKeeper@438] - Initiating client connection, connectString=localhost:2182 sessionTimeout=30000 watcher=org.apache.zookeeper.ZooKeeperMain$MyWatcher@506c589e
Welcome to ZooKeeper!
2017-01-03 10:04:47,159 [myid:] - INFO [main-SendThread(localhost:2182):ClientCnxn$SendThread@975] - Opening socket connection to server localhost/0:0:0:0:0:0:0:1:2182. Will not attempt to authenticate using SASL (unknown error)
JLine support is enabled
2017-01-03 10:04:48,381 [myid:] - INFO [main-SendThread(localhost:2182):ClientCnxn$SendThread@852] - Socket connection established to localhost/0:0:0:0:0:0:0:1:2182, initiating session
2017-01-03 10:04:48,562 [myid:] - INFO [main-SendThread(localhost:2182):ClientCnxn$SendThread@1235] - Session establishment complete on server localhost/0:0:0:0:0:0:0:1:2182, sessionId = 0x2595efcc86f0000, negotiated timeout = 30000

WATCHER::

WatchedEvent state:SyncConnected type:None path:null
[zk: localhost:2182(CONNECTED) 0] ls /
[zookeeper]
[zk: localhost:2182(CONNECTED) 1] []
```

- Here is the ZooKeeper3 Client instance running using the command
`$ zookeeper/zookeeper3/bin/zkCli.sh -server localhost:2183`


```
rakesh@localhost:~/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper3/bin

File Edit View Search Terminal Help
2017-01-03 10:05:57,005 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:java.home=/usr/java/jdk1.8.0_66/jre
2017-01-03 10:05:57,005 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:java.class.path=/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper3/bin/./build/classes:/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper3/bin/./build/lib/*:jar:/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper3/bin/./lib/slf4j-log4j12-1.6.1.jar:/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper3/bin/./lib/slf4j-api-1.6.1.jar:/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper3/bin/./lib/netty-3.7.0.Final.jar:/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper3/bin/./lib/log4j-1.2.16.jar:/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper3/bin/./lib/jline-0.9.94.jar:/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper3/bin/./zookeeper-3.4.6.jar:/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper3/bin/./src/java/lib/*:jar:/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper3/bin/./conf:
2017-01-03 10:05:57,005 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:java.library.path=/usr/java/packages/lib/amd64:/usr/lib64:/lib64:/lib:/usr/lib
2017-01-03 10:05:57,005 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:java.io.tmpdir=/tmp
2017-01-03 10:05:57,005 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:java.compiler=<NA>
2017-01-03 10:05:57,005 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:os.name=Linux
2017-01-03 10:05:57,005 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:os.arch=amd64
2017-01-03 10:05:57,005 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:os.version=3.10.0-327.4.5.el7.x86_64
2017-01-03 10:05:57,005 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:user.name=rakesh
2017-01-03 10:05:57,006 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:user.home=/home/rakesh
2017-01-03 10:05:57,006 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:user.dir=/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper3/bin
2017-01-03 10:05:57,007 [myid:] - INFO [main:ZooKeeper@438] - Initiating client connection, connectString=localhost:2183 sessionTimeout=30000 watcher=org.apache.zookeeper.ZooKeeperMain$MyWatcher@506c589e
2017-01-03 10:05:57,007 [myid:] - INFO [main:SendThread(Localhost:2183):ClientCnxn$SendThread@975] - Opening socket connection to server localhost/0:0:0:0:0:0:1:2183. Will not attempt to authenticate using SASL (unknown error)
Welcome to ZooKeeper!
Jline support is enabled
2017-01-03 10:05:57,280 [myid:] - INFO [main:SendThread(Localhost:2183):ClientCnxn$SendThread@852] - Socket connection established to localhost/0:0:0:0:0:0:1:2183, initiating session
2017-01-03 10:05:57,387 [myid:] - INFO [main:SendThread(Localhost:2183):ClientCnxn$SendThread@1235] - Session establishment complete on server localhost/0:0:0:0:0:0:1:2183, sessionId = 0x3595efd193c0000, negotiated timeout = 30000

WATCHER::
```



```
rakesh@localhost:~/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper3/bin

File Edit View Search Terminal Help
.6.1.jar:/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper3/bin/./lib/slf4j-api-1.6.1.jar:/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper3/bin/./lib/netty-3.7.0.Final.jar:/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper3/bin/./lib/log4j-1.2.16.jar:/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper3/bin/./lib/jline-0.9.94.jar:/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper3/bin/./zookeeper-3.4.6.jar:/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper3/bin/./src/java/lib/*:jar:/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper3/bin/./conf:
2017-01-03 10:05:57,005 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:java.library.path=/usr/java/packages/lib/amd64:/usr/lib64:/lib64:/lib:/usr/lib
2017-01-03 10:05:57,005 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:java.io.tmpdir=/tmp
2017-01-03 10:05:57,005 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:java.compiler=<NA>
2017-01-03 10:05:57,005 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:os.name=Linux
2017-01-03 10:05:57,005 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:os.arch=amd64
2017-01-03 10:05:57,005 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:os.version=3.10.0-327.4.5.el7.x86_64
2017-01-03 10:05:57,005 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:user.name=rakesh
2017-01-03 10:05:57,006 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:user.home=/home/rakesh
2017-01-03 10:05:57,006 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:user.dir=/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper3/bin
2017-01-03 10:05:57,007 [myid:] - INFO [main:ZooKeeper@438] - Initiating client connection, connectString=localhost:2183 sessionTimeout=30000 watcher=org.apache.zookeeper.ZooKeeperMain$MyWatcher@506c589e
2017-01-03 10:05:57,007 [myid:] - INFO [main:SendThread(Localhost:2183):ClientCnxn$SendThread@975] - Opening socket connection to server localhost/0:0:0:0:0:0:1:2183. Will not attempt to authenticate using SASL (unknown error)
Welcome to ZooKeeper!
Jline support is enabled
2017-01-03 10:05:57,280 [myid:] - INFO [main:SendThread(Localhost:2183):ClientCnxn$SendThread@852] - Socket connection established to localhost/0:0:0:0:0:0:1:2183, initiating session
2017-01-03 10:05:57,387 [myid:] - INFO [main:SendThread(Localhost:2183):ClientCnxn$SendThread@1235] - Session establishment complete on server localhost/0:0:0:0:0:0:1:2183, sessionId = 0x3595efd193c0000, negotiated timeout = 30000

WATCHER::

WatchedEvent state:SyncConnected type:None path:null
[zk: localhost:2183(CONNECTED) 0] 
```

4.Starting SolrCloud with Multiple External Zookeepers

We have started the individual Zookeeper Server and Client instances on our system. Now, let's start the Solr in Cloud Mode with these external Zookeepers.

To start Solr in Cloud Mode with created ZooKeeper instances on the same system use following command:

```
$ solr1/bin/solr/ start -c -p 8983 -z localhost:2184, localhost:2182, localhost:2183
```

A screenshot of a Linux terminal window. The window title is "Terminal" and the current directory is "/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/bin". The user has entered the command to start Solr in Cloud Mode with three external Zookeepers. The output shows that Solr was successfully started on port 8983.

```
rakesh@localhost:~/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/bin
File Edit View Search Terminal Help
[rakesh@localhost Desktop]$ cd solr-6.3.0/bin
[rakesh@localhost bin]$ ./solr stop -all
[rakesh@localhost bin]$ ./solr start -c -p 8983 -z localhost:2184,localhost:2182,localhost:2183
Archiving 1 old GC log files to /home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/server/logs/archived
Archiving 1 console log files to /home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/server/logs/archived
Rotating solr logs, keeping a max of 9 generations
Waiting up to 180 seconds to see Solr running on port 8983 [-]
Started Solr server on port 8983 (pid=32866). Happy searching!
[rakesh@localhost bin]$
```

This will start Solr instance in Cloud Mode on the port 8983.

We can visit <http://localhost:8983/solr> to check the status of SolrCloud.

The screenshot displays the Solr Admin web interface in a Mozilla Firefox browser window. The browser's address bar shows the URL `localhost:8983/solr/#/`. The page title is "Solr Admin - Mozilla Firefox".

The interface includes a sidebar on the left with navigation options: Dashboard, Logging, Cloud, Collections, Java Properties, Thread Dump, and a "Collection Sele..." dropdown. A status message indicates "No cores available" with a "Go and create one" button.

The main content area is divided into several sections:

- Instance:** Shows the "Start" time as "less than a minute ago".
- Versions:** A table listing installed components and their versions:

Component	Version
solr-spec	6.3.0
solr-impl	6.3.0 a66a44513ee8191e25b477372094bfa846450316 - shalin - 2016-11-0
lucene-spec	6.3.0
lucene-impl	6.3.0 a66a44513ee8191e25b477372094bfa846450316 - shalin - 2016-11-0
- JVM:** Shows the runtime as "Oracle Corporation Java HotSpot(TM) 64-Bit Server VM 1.8.0_66 25.66-b17".
- System:** A summary of system resources with progress bars:
 - Physical Memory: 96.4% (1.72 GB used, 1.78 GB total)
 - Swap Space: 18.4% (684.57 MB used, 3.62 GB total)
 - File Descriptor Count: 2.8% (116 used, 4096 total)
 - JVM-Memory: 10.7%

The bottom of the browser window shows the taskbar with open applications: Solr Admin - Mozilla Firefox, apache-solr-ref-guide-6.0.pdf, Pictures, and rakesh@localhost:~/Desktop/solr... The system tray shows the time as 1 / 4.

6. Starting Solr in Cloud Mode with External Zookeeper Ensemble on different Machines.

1. Creating Zookeeper Cluster on Different Systems

To create a cluster of Zookeeper on different systems, create three copies of the extracted ZooKeeper folder and name them as ZooKeeper1, ZooKeeper2 and Zookeeper3.

Now we will arrange a cluster of three nodes on the same host. Below is the cluster map:

Node 1: /Home/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper1/

Node 2: /Home/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper2/

Node 3: /Home/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper3/

After creating multiple copies of ZooKeeper, let's create a data directory to store the data and log files for Zookeeper ensemble.

Now, create three Zookeeper data directories to store data and log files for three individual ZooKeeper ensembles and name it as zook1, zook2 and zook3.

After replicating the ZooKeeper directories let's make the required changes in the zoo.cfg file for the Node1 by adding the IP address of the host we want to connect with.

```
tickTime=2000
```

```
initLimit=10
```

```
syncLimit=5
```

```
dataDir=/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookdata/zook1
```

```
clientPort=2184
```

```
server.1=localhost:2666:3666
```

```
server.2=localhost:2667:3667
```

```
server.3=localhost:2668:3668
```

```
server.4=192.168.100.14:2666:3666
```

```
server.5=192.168.100.14:2667:3667
```


The screenshot shows a gedit editor window titled '*zoo.cfg' with the following content:

```
initLimit=10
# The number of ticks that can pass between
# sending a request and getting an acknowledgement
syncLimit=5
# the directory where the snapshot is stored.
# do not use /tmp for storage, /tmp here is just
# example sakes.
dataDir=/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookdata/zook1
# the port at which the clients will connect
clientPort=2184
# the maximum number of client connections.
# increase this if you need to handle more clients
#maxClientCnxns=60
#
# Be sure to read the maintenance section of the
# administrator guide before turning on autopurge.
#
# http://zookeeper.apache.org/doc/current/zookeeperAdmin.html#sc_maintenance
#
# The number of snapshots to retain in dataDir
#autopurge.snapRetainCount=3
# Purge task interval in hours
# Set to "0" to disable auto purge feature
#autopurge.purgeInterval=1
server.1=localhost:2666:3666
server.2=localhost:2667:3667
server.3=localhost:2668:3668
server.4=192.168.100.14:2666:3666
server.5=192.168.100.14:2667:3667
```

The window title bar shows 'Applications', 'Places', and 'gedit'. The status bar at the bottom indicates 'Plain Text', 'Tab Width: 8', 'Ln 33, Col 34', and 'INS'. The taskbar at the bottom shows several open applications, including 'Inbox (2,170) - priyanka.suri27...', 'apache-sol-ref-guide-6.0.pdf', 'conf', 'rakesh@localhost:~/Desktop/so...', and '*zoo.cfg (/Desktop/zookeeper...'.

Here is the zoo.cfg file for the Node2. Let's add the IP address of the host we want to connect.

```
tickTime=2000
```

```
initLimit=10
```

```
syncLimit=5
```

```
dataDir=/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookdata/zook2
```

```
clientPort=2182
```

```
server.1=localhost:2666:3666
```

```
server.2=localhost:2667:3667
```

```
server.3=localhost:2668:3668
```

```
server.4=192.168.100.14:2666:3666
```

```
server.5=192.168.100.14:2667:3667
```


The screenshot shows a gedit text editor window titled '*zoo.cfg' with the file path '~/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper2/conf'. The window contains the following configuration text:

```
initLimit=10
# The number of ticks that can pass between
# sending a request and getting an acknowledgement
syncLimit=5
# the directory where the snapshot is stored.
# do not use /tmp for storage, /tmp here is just
# example sakes.
dataDir=/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookdata/zook2
# the port at which the clients will connect
clientPort=2182
# the maximum number of client connections.
# increase this if you need to handle more clients
#maxClientCnxns=60
#
# Be sure to read the maintenance section of the
# administrator guide before turning on autopurge.
#
# http://zookeeper.apache.org/doc/current/zookeeperAdmin.html#sc_maintenance
#
# The number of snapshots to retain in dataDir
#autopurge.snapRetainCount=3
# Purge task interval in hours
# Set to "0" to disable auto purge feature
#autopurge.purgeInterval=1
server.1=localhost:2666:3666
server.2=localhost:2667:3667
server.3=localhost:2668:3668
server.4=192.168.100.14:2666:3666
server.5=192.168.100.14:2667:3667
```

The window's status bar at the bottom indicates 'Plain Text', 'Tab Width: 8', 'Ln 33, Col 34', and 'INS'. The taskbar at the bottom shows several open applications, including an inbox, a PDF file, a 'conf' directory, and the current gedit window.

Here is the zoo.cfg file for the Node3. Let's add the IP address of the host we want to connect.

```
tickTime=2000
```

```
initLimit=10
```

```
syncLimit=5
```

```
dataDir=/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookdata/zook2
```

```
clientPort=2183
```

```
server.1=localhost:2666:3666
```

```
server.2=localhost:2667:3667
```

```
server.3=localhost:2668:3668
```

```
server.4=192.168.100.14:2666:3666
```

```
server.5=192.168.100.14:2667:3667
```


The screenshot shows a gedit text editor window titled '*zoo.cfg' with the file path '~/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper3/conf'. The editor contains the following configuration text:

```
initLimit=10
# The number of ticks that can pass between
# sending a request and getting an acknowledgement
syncLimit=5
# the directory where the snapshot is stored.
# do not use /tmp for storage, /tmp here is just
# example sakes.
dataDir=/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookdata/zook3
# the port at which the clients will connect
clientPort=2183
# the maximum number of client connections.
# increase this if you need to handle more clients
#maxClientCnxns=60
#
# Be sure to read the maintenance section of the
# administrator guide before turning on autopurge.
#
# http://zookeeper.apache.org/doc/current/zookeeperAdmin.html#sc_maintenance
#
# The number of snapshots to retain in dataDir
#autopurge.snapRetainCount=3
# Purge task interval in hours
# Set to "0" to disable auto purge feature
#autopurge.purgeInterval=1
server.1=localhost:2666:3666
server.2=localhost:2667:3667
server.3=localhost:2668:3668
server.4=192.168.100.14:2666:3666
server.5=192.168.100.14:2667:3667
```

The editor interface includes a menu bar with 'Open' and 'Save' options, and a status bar at the bottom showing 'Plain Text', 'Tab Width: 8', 'Ln 33, Col 34', and 'INS'. The taskbar at the bottom shows several open applications, including an inbox, a PDF viewer, and the current gedit window.

2. Running Zookeeper Client

To run Zookeeper Client with different hosts, use the command:

```
$. /zkCli.sh -server 192.168.100.14:2184
```



```
rakesh@localhost:~/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper1/bin
File Edit View Search Terminal Help
[rakesh@localhost bin]$ ./zkCli.sh -server 192.168.100.14:2184
Connecting to 192.168.100.14:2184
2017-01-03 11:18:29,010 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:zookeeper.version=3.4.6-1569965, built on 02/20/2014 09:09 GMT
2017-01-03 11:18:29,020 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:host.name=localhost
2017-01-03 11:18:29,021 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:java.version=1.8.0_66
2017-01-03 11:18:29,023 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:java.vendor=Oracle Corporation
2017-01-03 11:18:29,023 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:java.home=/usr/java/jdk1.8.0_66/jre
2017-01-03 11:18:29,023 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:java.class.path=/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper1/bin/./build/classes:/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper1/bin/./build/lib/*:jar:/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper1/bin/./lib/slf4j-log4j12-1.6.1.jar:/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper1/bin/./lib/slf4j-api-1.6.1.jar:/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper1/bin/./lib/netty-3.7.0.Final.jar:/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper1/bin/./lib/log4j-1.2.16.jar:/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper1/bin/./lib/jline-0.9.94.jar:/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper1/bin/./src/java/lib/*:jar:/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper1/bin/./conf:
2017-01-03 11:18:29,023 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:java.library.path=/usr/java/packages/lib/amd64:/usr/lib64:/lib64:/lib:/usr/lib
2017-01-03 11:18:29,023 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:java.io.tmpdir=/tmp
2017-01-03 11:18:29,024 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:java.compiler=<NA>
2017-01-03 11:18:29,024 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:os.name=Linux
2017-01-03 11:18:29,024 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:os.arch=amd64
2017-01-03 11:18:29,024 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:os.version=3.10.0-327.4.5.el7.x86_64
2017-01-03 11:18:29,024 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:user.name=rakesh
2017-01-03 11:18:29,024 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:user.home=/home/rakesh
2017-01-03 11:18:29,024 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:user.dir=/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper1/bin
2017-01-03 11:18:29,025 [myid:] - INFO [main:ZooKeeper@438] - Initiating client connection, connectString=192.168.100.14:2184 sessionTimeout=30000
watcher=org.apache.zookeeper.ZooKeeperMain$MyWatcher@506c589e
Welcome to ZooKeeper!
2017-01-03 11:18:29,264 [myid:] - INFO [main-SendThread(192.168.100.14:2184):ClientCnxn$SendThread@975] - Opening socket connection to server 192.168.100.14/192.168.100.14:2184. Will not attempt to authenticate using SASL (unknown error)
JLine support is enabled
```



```
rakesh@localhost:~/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper1/bin
File Edit View Search Terminal Help
./lib/slf4j-api-1.6.1.jar:/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper1/bin/./lib/netty-3.7.0.Final.jar:/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper1/bin/./lib/log4j-1.2.16.jar:/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper1/bin/./lib/jline-0.9.94.jar:/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper1/bin/./zookeeper-3.4.6.jar:/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper1/bin/./src/java/lib/*:jar:/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper1/bin/./conf:
2017-01-03 11:18:29,023 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:java.library.path=/usr/java/packages/lib/amd64:/usr/lib64:/lib64:/lib:/usr/lib
2017-01-03 11:18:29,023 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:java.io.tmpdir=/tmp
2017-01-03 11:18:29,024 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:java.compiler=<NA>
2017-01-03 11:18:29,024 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:os.name=Linux
2017-01-03 11:18:29,024 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:os.arch=amd64
2017-01-03 11:18:29,024 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:os.version=3.10.0-327.4.5.el7.x86_64
2017-01-03 11:18:29,024 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:user.name=rakesh
2017-01-03 11:18:29,024 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:user.home=/home/rakesh
2017-01-03 11:18:29,024 [myid:] - INFO [main:Environment@100] - Client environment:user.dir=/home/rakesh/Desktop/zookeeper/zookeeper1/bin
2017-01-03 11:18:29,025 [myid:] - INFO [main:ZooKeeper@438] - Initiating client connection, connectString=192.168.100.14:2184 sessionTimeout=30000
watcher=org.apache.zookeeper.ZooKeeperMain$MyWatcher@506c589e
Welcome to ZooKeeper!
2017-01-03 11:18:29,264 [myid:] - INFO [main-SendThread(192.168.100.14:2184):ClientCnxn$SendThread@975] - Opening socket connection to server 192.168.100.14/192.168.100.14:2184. Will not attempt to authenticate using SASL (unknown error)
JLine support is enabled
2017-01-03 11:18:30,505 [myid:] - INFO [main-SendThread(192.168.100.14:2184):ClientCnxn$SendThread@852] - Socket connection established to 192.168.100.14/192.168.100.14:2184, initiating session
2017-01-03 11:18:30,533 [myid:] - INFO [main-SendThread(192.168.100.14:2184):ClientCnxn$SendThread@1235] - Session establishment complete on server 192.168.100.14/192.168.100.14:2184, sessionId = 0x15962dd664f0001, negotiated timeout = 30000

WATCHER::

WatchedEvent state:SyncConnected type:None path:null
[zookeeper:192.168.100.14:2184(CONNECTED) 0]
```

3.Starting Solr in Cloud Mode with multiple ZooKeepers on Different Machines

To start Solr in Cloud mode with the created ZooKeeper instances on different machine use the following command:

```
$. /solr start -c -p 8984 -z localhost:2184,localhost:2182,localhost:2183,192.168.100.14:2184, 192.168.100.14:2182
```



```
rakesh@localhost:~/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/solr2
File Edit View Search Terminal Help
[rakesh@localhost solr-6.3.0]$ cd solr2
[rakesh@localhost solr2]$ cd bin
[rakesh@localhost bin]$ ./solr start -c -p 8984 -z 192.168.100.14:2184
Archiving 1 old GC log files to /home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/solr2/server/logs/archived
Archiving 1 console log files to /home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/solr2/server/logs/archived
Rotating solr logs, keeping a max of 9 generations
Waiting up to 180 seconds to see Solr running on port 8984 [-]
Started Solr server on port 8984 (pid=5720). Happy searching!
```

We can visit localhost:8986 on the web browser to redirect to the Solr Cloud GUI.

4. Creating Collection

Now, we will create a collection using the following command after establishing connection between Solr and Zookeepers on different machines.

```
$. /bin/solr create_collection -c Priyanka1 -d data_driven_schema_configs -shards 3 -replicationFactor 2 -p 8984
```



```
rakesh@localhost:~/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/solr2
File Edit View Search Terminal Help
If not specified, the script will search the local system for a running
Solr instance and will use the port of the first server it finds.

[rakesh@localhost solr2]$ ./bin/solr create_collection -c Priyanka1 -d data_driven_schema_configs -shards 3 -replicationFactor 2 -p 8984
Connecting to ZooKeeper at 192.168.100.14:2184 ...
Uploading /home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/solr2/server/solr/configsets/data_driven_schema_configs/conf for config Priyanka1 to ZooKeeper at 192.168.100.14:2184
Creating new collection 'Priyanka1' using command:
http://localhost:8984/solr/admin/collections?action=CREATE&name=Priyanka1&numShards=3&replicationFactor=2&maxShardsPerNode=3&collection.configName=Priyanka1
{
  "responseHeader":{
    "status":0,
    "QTime":13766,
    "success":{
      "192.168.100.14:8983_solr":{
        "responseHeader":{
          "status":0,
          "QTime":12360,
          "core":"Priyanka1_shard3_replica1"},
        "192.168.100.11:8984_solr":{
          "responseHeader":{
            "status":0,
            "QTime":12900,
            "core":"Priyanka1_shard2_replica2"}}}
    }
  }
}
[rakesh@localhost solr2]$
```

Now, let's visit localhost:8984 to check the leader and follower allocation between Solr on different machine.

Here, we can see in the second collection that the replicas of the shards created is divided between Solr on host 192.168.100.14 & 192.168.100.11 and accordingly leader and follower is assigned between the hosts on two different machine.

5.Posting Documents to the Collection

To post the documents to the Collection created previously we will use the following command:

```
$. /bin/post -c Priyanka1 example/exampledocs/*.xml -p 8984
```



```
rakesh@localhost:~/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/solr2
File Edit View Search Terminal Help
"QTime":12900},
"core":"Priyanka1_shard2_replica2"}}}
[rakesh@localhost solr2]$ ./bin/post -c Priyanka1 example/exampledocs/*.xml -p 8984
/usr/java/jdk1.8.0_66/bin/java -classpath /home/rakesh/Desktop/solr-6.3.0/solr2/dist/solr-core-6.3.0.jar -Dauto=yes -Dport=8984 -Dc=Priyanka1 -Ddata=files org.apache.solr.util.SimplePostTool example/exampledocs/gb18030-example.xml example/exampledocs/hd.xml example/exampledocs/ipod_other.xml example/exampledocs/ipod_video.xml example/exampledocs/manufacturers.xml example/exampledocs/mem.xml example/exampledocs/money.xml example/exampledocs/monitor2.xml example/exampledocs/monitor.xml example/exampledocs/mp500.xml example/exampledocs/sd500.xml example/exampledocs/solr.xml example/exampledocs/utf8-example.xml example/exampledocs/vidcard.xml
SimplePostTool version 5.0.0
Posting files to [base] url http://localhost:8984/solr/Priyanka1/update...
Entering auto mode. File endings considered are xml,json,jsonl, csv,pdf,doc,docx,ppt,pptx,xls,xlsx,odt,odp,ods,ott,otp,ots,rtf,htm,html,txt,log
POSTing file gb18030-example.xml (application/xml) to [base]
POSTing file hd.xml (application/xml) to [base]
POSTing file ipod_other.xml (application/xml) to [base]
POSTing file ipod_video.xml (application/xml) to [base]
POSTing file manufacturers.xml (application/xml) to [base]
POSTing file mem.xml (application/xml) to [base]
POSTing file money.xml (application/xml) to [base]
POSTing file monitor2.xml (application/xml) to [base]
POSTing file monitor.xml (application/xml) to [base]
POSTing file mp500.xml (application/xml) to [base]
POSTing file sd500.xml (application/xml) to [base]
POSTing file solr.xml (application/xml) to [base]
POSTing file utf8-example.xml (application/xml) to [base]
POSTing file vidcard.xml (application/xml) to [base]
14 files indexed.
COMMITting Solr index changes to http://localhost:8984/solr/Priyanka1/update...
Time spent: 0:00:34.406
[rakesh@localhost solr2]$
```

We have successfully posted documents to the collection created. Since, we are connecting Solr and ZooKeepers on two different machines, the created collection will be replicated to both the hosts.

Now, let's run the query on the posted documents in the next section.

6. Running Query on the documents posted in the Collection

To run the query, we will log into <http://localhost:8984/solr> on the web browser and move to the query section in the created collection.

The screenshot shows the Solr Admin web interface in a Mozilla Firefox browser. The address bar displays `localhost:8984/solr/#/Priyanka1/query`. The left sidebar contains navigation options like Dashboard, Logging, Cloud, Collections, Java Properties, Thread Dump, and a dropdown menu for the collection 'Priyanka1'. The main content area is titled 'Request-Handler (qt) /select' and shows a 'common' section with a 'q' field containing '*:*'. Below this, there are fields for 'fq', 'sort', 'start, rows' (set to 0 and 10), 'fl', 'df', and 'Raw Query Parameters'. The right pane displays the JSON response from the query, including a 'responseHeader' with status and time, and a 'response' object with 'numFound': 32 and a list of document objects. The first document shown is:

```
{
  "id": "IW-02",
  "name": ["iPod & iPod Mini USB 2.0 Cable"],
  "manu": ["Belkin"],
  "manu_id_s": "belkin",
  "cat": ["electronics",
    "connector"],
  "features": ["car power adapter for iPod, white"],
  "weight": [2.0],
  "price": [11.5],
  "popularity": [1],
}
```

The screenshot shows the Solr Admin web interface in a Mozilla Firefox browser. The address bar displays `localhost:8984/solr/#/Priyanka1/query`. The left sidebar contains navigation options like hl, facet, spatial, spellcheck, and an 'Execute Query' button. The main content area shows the 'Raw Query Parameters' section with a 'q' field containing '*:*'. The right pane displays the JSON response from the query, including a 'responseHeader' with status and time, and a 'response' object with 'numFound': 3 and a list of document objects. The first document shown is:

```
{
  "id": "belkin",
  "compName_s": "Belkin",
  "address_s": "12045 E. Waterfront Drive Playa Vista, CA 90094",
  "_version_": 1555571012333993984,
}
{
  "id": "maxtor",
  "compName_s": "Maxtor Corporation",
  "address_s": "920 Disc Drive Scotts Valley, CA 95066",
  "_version_": 1555571012344479744,
}
{
  "id": "TWINX2048-3200PRO",
  "name": ["CORSAIR XMS 2GB (2 x 1GB) 184-Pin DDR SDRAM Unbuffered DDR 400 (PC 3200) Dual Channel Kit System Memory"],
  "manu": ["Corsair Microsystems Inc."],
  "manu_id_s": "corsair",
  "cat": ["electronics",
    "memory"],
  "features": ["CAS latency 2, 2-3-3-6 timing, 2.75v, unbuffered, heat-spreader"],
  "price": [185.0],
  "popularity": [5],
  "inStock": [true],
  "store": ["37, 7752, -122, 4232"],
  "manufacturedate_dt": "2006-02-13T15:26:37Z",
  "payloads": ["electronics[6.0 memory|3.0]"],
  "_version_": 1555571012477648896,
}
```


We can fire a query according to the requirements in the -q field. Solr GUI also gives the feasibility to apply filters on the query.

7.Shutdown Solr

To end Solr, we can use the following command.

```
$ ./bin/solr stop
```

This will shutdown Solr cleanly.

Solr is fairly robust. In the situations of OS or disk crashes, it is unlikely that Solr's index will become corrupted.

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